

side just after the double boundary formation in the electrolysis of (0.005 M) $K_2Cr_2O_7$ solution in a 16 mm o.d. W-tube, the current density gradually increases from a very low value of 0.2 to about 2.5-3 mA and remains steady at that point thereafter. Besides, the alkaline dichromate colour at the cathode side gradually diminishes and becomes completely colourless after about one week. On the otherhand, the colour of the anode limb becomes darker. Therefore, we come across a situation in which the double boundary formation which is very much common with a W-tube, can be converted to a single boundary just by adding excess electrolyte. Similar phenomenon takes place even with the addition of solid $K_2Cr_2O_7$ from both cathode and anode sides at the same time.

Effect of temperature : Temperature has a pronounced effect on the boundary formation in a W-tube. At higher temperature ($\sim 45^\circ$), the electrolysis of 0.005 M $K_2Cr_2O_7$ solution in a W-tube of 16 mm o.d. and at 20 mA current density gives single boundary at the anode bend. After about 48 h current decreases to 10 mA. On cooling down the electrolytic cell to room temperature double boundary forms and the current density decreases to 0.5 mA. At this stage if the temperature is again increased to 45° , the boundary does not diffuse. With wider tube (32 mm o.d.) whose middle part is of the same height as the cathode and the anode limb, electrolysis of 0.01 M chromic acid at 45° in a thermostat and 15 mA current density does not show any boundary formation for overnight and a few cm³ of gas usually termed as IZ-gas, at the middle portion of the tube is formed. Similar phenomenon is observed with 0.005 M $K_2Cr_2O_7$ solution at 45° . Electrolysis of 0.005 M $K_2Cr_2O_7$ solution in such tube at room temperature takes about 48 h for double boundary formation. Temperature is then increased to 45° , when the boundary diffused and current increased to 12 mA and remained steady thereafter.

Lilliput electrodes—its effect : On electrolysis with lilliput electrodes as cathode and anode, a colourless band first appears at the cathode bend and another boundary appears at the anode bend so that the colour inside the tube from anode to cathode side becomes orange-yellow - colourless band-light yellow. Although, current decreases to 5 mA, the colourless band remains as it is. With the cathode of lilliput size and the foil type anode, the boundary forms quickly. After double boundary formation the colourless band disappears and intermediate zone becomes totally colourless. When the case is reversed by taking lilliput electrode as anode and foil electrode as cathode, little longer time is required for double boundary formation, colourless band remaining at the cathode bend.

Other set-ups equivalent to W-tube : 0.0025 M $K_2Cr_2O_7$ is electrolysed in the set up comprising of two 250 ml beakers connected by an inverted U-tube of 10 mm o.d. platinum foil electrodes are introduced separately into the beakers. Current

is passed directly from D.C. mains and within 4 h it becomes 26 mA. No sharp boundary is formed but the solution in the beaker containing the anode becomes darker in colour and that in the other one becomes light yellow. Colour inside the connecting tube becomes deep yellow but on continued electrolysis for overnight, current decreases to 0.8 mA and the middle part becomes colourless. Then another beaker is introduced at the middle to the preceding set-up and connected as before by another inverted U-tube of 10 mm o.d. Here electrolysis of 0.0025 M $K_2Cr_2O_7$ solution for overnight makes only one connecting tube nearer the cathode colourless. The solution in the beaker containing cathode becomes light yellow while two other beakers are orange in colour and the second connecting tube is yellow in colour. This situation remains as it is even on further electrolysis.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to late Prof. S. R. Palit for helpful suggestion and discussion.

References

1. S. R. PALIT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **49**, 963.
2. S. R. PALIT, *Indian J. Phys.*, 1972, **46**, 430.
3. S. R. PALIT and M. GUHA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **51**, 518.
4. S. R. PALIT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 114.
5. S. R. PALIT, *J. Soc. Dyers Colour.*, 1975, 346.
6. S. K. SENGUPTA and S. R. PALIT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 724.

Electrochemical Oxidation of Alcohol Held in the Cathode Chamber to Acetic Acid Through Non-Faradaic Electrolysis

SUBHALAKSHMI GHOSH

Department of Physical Chemistry, Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Calcutta-700 032

Manuscript received 30 November 1983, accepted 21 July 1984

It has been earlier postulated¹ that co-liberation (*i.e.* liberation of a mixture of hydrogen and oxygen) at the cathode during non-Faradaic electrolysis is caused by the formation of $(H_2O)_x^+$ at the anode due to high dielectric constant of water. This H_2O^+ is a free radical ion of oxidative character and so is expected to oxidise substances present in its path of migration to the cathode. Indeed this has been found² to be true, even very stable compounds like chlorobenzene, nitrobenzene, *etc* being oxidised when placed in the intermediate zone in the path of the current. If our idea be correct, H_2O^+ formed at the anode would travel towards the cathode and may oxidise substances present at the cathode chamber, though in normal electrolysis the cathode chamber is a seat of reducing activity. Thus under such conditions we may expect to observe the abnormal phenomenon of oxidation in the cathode

chamber. In this note we report such facile oxidation of alcohol held in the cathode chamber presumably caused by the above mechanism.

Experimental

The apparatus was an ordinary U-tube (20 cm \times 18 mm o.d.) with a fine fritted glass partition at the bottom (the size not critical). The electrodes were bright platinum foils (1 cm \times 1 cm). The cathode side was fitted with a cork through which passed a long vertical tube to take care of the electro-osmotic rise. The catholyte is a 1% solution of ethyl alcohol whereas the anolyte is distilled water. 230 V from D.C. mains are directly applied. Water being highly non-conducting only a few hundred microamperes passed at the beginning. A higher D.C. voltage may be applied if available. The current slowly rose to about 1 mA and somewhat beyond. Due to the high electro-osmotic rise of distilled water at the cathode side, 0.01 N Na_2SO_4 or 0.01 N H_2SO_4 solution was better used instead. About 1-4 mA current was passed for 24 h. Few experiments were also done in a simple U-tube (30 cm \times 32 mm o.d.) as used in our previous experiments for the study of non-Faradaic electrolysis⁸. In such U-tube the required amount of alcohol was added very carefully from the cathode side just after the electrolysis started. Electro-osmosis did not take place due to the absence of fritted glass partition at the bottom. Therefore, the experiment was done even with distilled water. But due to very low current density, acid conversion was less than that with 0.01 N or 0.001 N H_2SO_4 solution.

What happens is that H_3O^+ enters the cathode chamber and oxidises the alcohol to acetic acid. The acetic acid as it forms migrates to the anode chamber and so almost the whole product of oxidation formed inside the cathode chamber collects in the anolyte. The amount of acetic acid formed is found by titration with 0.1 N NaOH using phenolphthalein as indicator. Since 4 F are theoretically needed to convert 1 mole alcohol to 1 mole acetic acid ($\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH} + 2\text{O} = \text{CH}_3\text{COOH} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$) and since 1 mA per day is approximately equal to 1 meqv., it is easily seen that if the efficiency is cent per cent, 10 ml 0.1 N alkali would be the titre in 4 days at current strength of 1 mA. The actual efficiency is found to be about 70 to 90 per cent, a remarkable yield.

It may be thought that alcohol is diffusing to the anode chamber and getting oxidised there. The contrary is proved by the fact that in a control experiment no detectable amount of alcohol (acid $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ test) is found in the anode chamber consistent with the extremely slow rate of diffusion through such fine 'frit'. Even a N $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ solution shows no detectable diffusion in a week. Furthermore, electro-osmotic flow takes place in the reverse direction towards the cathode. A portion (5 to 10%) of acetic acid formed is also found in the cathode chamber itself.

Not only ethyl alcohol, but many other substances are reacted upon in the same way. For example, methyl alcohol is oxidised to formic acid and carbon dioxide, other alcohols to the corresponding acids, urea to ammonia and so on which will be reported in a separate publication. We record here only the remarkable fact that oxidation may take place even in the catholyte with high current efficiency but low power efficiency. Efforts are being made to remove the latter hurdle in order to make the process attractive and cost-efficient.

Acknowledgement

The work has been carried out under the guidance of late Professor S. R. Palit.

References

1. S. R. PALIT and S. GHOSH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 494.
2. S. R. PALIT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **50**, 625.
3. S. R. PALIT and S. GHOSH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 1099.

Ultraviolet and Visible Spectral Studies of Anthraquinonyl and Other Hydroxytriazenes

D. N. PUROHIT

Department of Chemistry, S. B. S. H., M. L. Sukhadia University, Udaipur-313 001

Manuscript received 26 December 1983, revised 12 June 1984, accepted 17 June 1984

HYDROXYTRIAZENES, also called diazohydroxyamino compounds and triazen oxides¹ have been established as an important group of chelating agents^{2,3}. There is a growing interest⁴⁻⁷ in these compounds. In this communication the ultraviolet and visible spectral studies of nine hydroxytriazenes have been reported.

Experimental

The ultraviolet and visible absorption spectra were taken in absolute alcohol on a Beckmann DB spectrophotometer using quartz and glass cells of 1.0 cm pathlength. The results obtained (λ_{max} , $\log \epsilon$) are given in Table 1.

From Table 1 it is not possible to make any exact correlation with the structure. Still the following points are noteworthy.

(a) Compounds no. 1, 2 and 3 show two absorption maxima. The first one appears at 418-420 nm which may be assigned to $n-\pi^*$ transition. The second one appears in the range 300-388 nm and specifically at 347 ± 5 nm in compounds no. 1, 2 and 3. It seems to be due to the conjugation between $-\text{N}=\text{N}-$ and the aryl nucleus and may be designated as $\pi-\pi^*$ transition.